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**A new monograph by G. Sama (2023) on Longicorn beetles
(Coleoptera, Cerambycidae) of North Africa:
remarks and discussion**

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Key words: Coleoptera, Cerambycidae, North Africa, taxonomy, zoogeography.

Abstract: More than 40 remarks are proposed. Each remark is equipped with a page number of the monograph it is connected with. No new taxa, no new combinations, no new ranks are proposed here, but several original geographical data are shown. Many taxonomy, geography or references data are discussed. Several wrong statements (mistakes or misprints) are corrected.

Introduction

A new great fundamental monograph on North African Cerambycidae by Sama (2023) contains many taxonomical modifications. Many novations reflect considerable progress in longicorn taxonomy, others are connected with his personal opinion, but certain positions are unacceptable and must be corrected. I try to show several of the most interesting positions with special attention to doubtful conclusions.

Results

p. 55; According to Sama (2023), *Polyarthron pectinicornе* (Fabricius, 1892) is a variable species without subspecies. But a map of its area (Sama, 2023: 57) shows 4 big subspecies, and three of them are divided in smaller taxa.

p. 61. According to Sama (2023), *Mesoprionus besikanus* (Fairmaire, 1855) = *M. lefebvrei* (Marseul, 1856) = *Prionus tangerianus* Sláma, 1996 = *Prionus batelkai* Sláma, 1996.

M.A. Lazarev

pp. 22, 68. Rhamnusiini Danilevsky, 1997 is accepted (Sama, 2023: 22), as well as Rhamnusiini Sama, Švácha & Danilevsky, 2009 (Sama, 2023: 68), though the later publication does not exist.

pp. 22, 71-72. *Rhagium inquisitor inquisitor* (L.) is recorded for Algeria (Sama, 2023: 71), though “adults not emerged (!)” and for Morocco (Sama, 2023: 22). *Rh. i. cedri* Reymond, 1954 is recorded for Algeria (Sama, 2023: 22).

pp. 22, 72. *Grammoptera* was included in Rhagiini by G. Sama.

pp. 63-64. According to Sama (2023), Dorcasominae Lacordaire, 1869 and Apatophyseinae Lacordaire, 1869 are different subfamilies, as it was proposed by Danilevsky (2010: 48): “*Apatophyseinae*: the genus *Apatophysis* Chevrolat, 1860 is not included in the subfamily Dorcasominae Lacordaire, 1868 (as in Özdikmen, 2008), because of significant distinctive imaginal (divided stridulatory plate in *Dorcasomus* Audinet-Serville, 1834) and larval characters. Consequently, the subfamily Apatophyseinae Lacordaire, 1869 is kept as valid in the present Catalogue.” A great monograph on Madagascan Apatophyseinae (Villiers, Quentin & Vives, 2011) also accepted Dorcasominae as valid name.

p. 82. Incorrect synonymy was proposed by G.Sama: *Stictoleptura* Casey, 1924 = *Aredolpona* Nakane & K. Ohbayashi, 1957 = *Melanoleptura* Miroshnikov, 1998 = *Batesiata* Miroshnikov, 1998. All such names are valid as subgenera of *Stictoleptura* Casey, 1924.

p. 87. *Stictoleptura scutellata maritima* Sláma, 2015 is a valid name of a subspecies from Aiguines (France), but not a synonym of *S. s. scutellata* (Fabricius, 1781), as it was proposed by G. Sama.

p. 92. According to Sama (2023), *Stenurella* Villiers, 1974 = *Iberostenurella* Özdikmen, 2013 = *Crassostenurella* Özdikmen, 2013 = *Nigrostenurella* Özdikmen, 2013 = *Priscostenurella* Özdikmen, 2013 = *Stenurelloides* Özdikmen, 2013.

M.A. Lazarev

p. 98. Valid genera names *Arhopalus* Audinet-Serville, 1834 and *Cephalocrius* Sharp, 1905 were regarded by G. Sama as synonyms.

p. 114. According to Sama (2023), Lygrini Sama, 2008 = Pelossini Tavakilian, 2013.

p. 120. *Phoracantha recurva* was recorded for Algeria by G. Sama.

p. 125. *Hesperophanes andresi* Sama & Rapuzzi, 2006 was recorded for Tunis by G. Sama.

p. 142. *Icosium* P. H. Lucas, 1854 was placed in Hesperophanini (Daramina) by G. Sama.

p. 148. Natural divisions of *Cerambyx* Linnaeus, 1758 in two subgenera: *Cerambyx* s. str. and *Microcerambyx* Mikšić & Georgijevic, 1973 (= *Mesocerambyx* Zagaikевич, 1991) was not accepted by G. Sama.

p. 176. According to G. Sama, Nathriini Linsley, 1963 = Leptidiini Fairmaire, 1864 (type genus *Leptidea*, Mulsant, 1839, nec Billberg, 1820) = Psebiini Martins, 2003, nec Lecordaire, 1868.

pp. 180-183. A tribe for *Oxilus* Buquet, 1859, *Bolivarita* Escalera, 1914 and *Ossibia* Pascoe, 1867 was not denoted by G.Sama. Traditionally all three genera were regarded in Obriini.

A single known specimen of *Oxilus* from Egypt was not identified by G. Sama.

p. 181. Sama (2023) published a lectotype designation for *Bolivarita oculata* Escalera, 1914, while it was designated before by Trócoli (2019: 159).

p. 199. Hylotrupini Zagajkevich, 1991 is a valid name, but not a synonym of Callidiini Kirby, 1837, as it was proposed by G. Sama.

M.A. Lazarev

p. 200. *Chalcoturanium* Jankowsky, 1934 must be preserved as a subgenus of *Turanium* Baeckmann, 1922, but not as a valid genus name as it was proposed by G. Sama.

p. 201. According to G. Sama, Algerian populations of *Ropalopus* can demonstrate characters of *R. ungaricus* Herbst, 1784, *R. insubricus* Germar, 1824 or *R. siculus* Stierlin, 1863); each one cannot be definitely identified. In general all three taxa are forms of one species.

p. 209-210. *Poecilium* Fairmaire, 1864 is a subgenus of *Phymatodes* Mulsant, 1839, as well as *Phymatoderus* Reitter, 1913, *Phymatodellus* Reitter, 1913 and *Paraphymatodes* Plavilstshikov, 1934, while all 3 were wrongly regarded by G.Sama as synonymes of a genus name *Poecilium* Fairmaire, 1864.

p. 212. *Lucasianus* Pic, 1891 was placed in Callidiini by G. Sama.

p. 214. Anaglyptini Lacordaire, 1868 is a valid name, but not a synonym of Clytini Mulsant, 1839, as it was proposed by G. Sama.

p. 221. Valid genera names *Plagionotus* Mulsant, 1842, *Echinocerus* Mulsant, 1862 and *Neoplagonotus* Kasatkin, 2005 are not synonymes as it was proposed by G. Sama.

p. 225. According to Sama (2023), *Chlorophorus* Chevrolat, 1863 = *Crassofasciatus* Özdikmen, 2011 = *Humeromaculatus* Özdikmen, 2011 = *Immaculatus* Özdikmen, 2011 = *Perderomaculatus* Özdikmen, 2011.

p. 227. *Chlorophorus glaucus* (Fabricius, 1781) was regarded as a species by G. Sama.

p. 239. Dorcadionini J. Thomson, 1860 is a valid name, but not a synonym of Lamiini Latreille, 1825 as it was proposed by G. Sama.

M.A. Lazarev

p. 243. *Parmena algerica* Catelnau, 1840 (often also recorded as *algerica* Laporte, 1840 - Laporte Francis Louis Nompar de Caumont, Comte de Castelnau) was accepted by G.Sama as a valid name, as well as *P. pubescens* (Dalman, 1817) was recorded for Libya. The original publication was not shown in the References to the monograph.

p. 245. According to Sama (2023), *Monochamus galloprovincialis* (Olivier, 1800) is rather different from different areas. Specimens from northern Morocco are just same as *M.g. pistor* (Germar, 1818) from Slovenia; while populations from Algeria are similar to reddish specimens from southern France, so subspecies divisions in *M. galloprovincialis* are not acceptable.

p. 250. *Eunidiini* is a valid name, but not *Eunidiina* Sama, 2023 inside *Apomecynini* by Sama (2023).

p. 251. *Eunidia nigricans* Breuning, 1942d was recorded for Egypt-Sudan border by G.Sama.

p. 254. *Smaragdula* Pesarini & Sabbadini, 2004 is not a synonym of *Agapanthia* Audinet-Serville, 1835, as it was proposed by G. Sama, but a valid subgenus name.

p. 257. Several valid subgenera names: *Stichodera* Pesarini & Sabbadini, 2004, *Drosotrichia* Pesarini & Sabbadini, 2004, *Agapanthoplia* Pesarini & Sabbadini, 2004, *Amurobia* Pesarini & Sabbadini, 2004, *Chinosticta* Pesarini & Sabbadini, 2004, *Homoblephara* Pesarini & Sabbadini, 2004 and *Synthapsia* Pesarini & Sabbadini, 2004 were wrongly regarded by Sama (2023) as synonyms of *Epoetes* Gistel, 1857.

p. 278. *Crossotus subocellatus heimschi* Peyerimhoff, 1922 was accepted by Sama (2023) as “**stat. nov.**”, but it was published by him before (Sama & Löbl, 2010).

M.A. Lazarev

p. 286. *Exocentrini* Pascoe, 1864 is a valid name, but not a synonym of *Pogonocherini* Mulsant, 1939 as it was proposed by G. Sama.

p. 287. *Pityphilus* Mulsant, 1862 is a valid subgenus name, but not a synonym of *Pogonocherus* Dejean, 1821, as it was proposed by G. Sama.

p. 300. *Obereini* Thomson, 1864 was just a mistake by Sama (2023); *Phytoeciini* Mulsant, 1839 = *Obereini* Thomson, 1864

p. 316. A subgenus name *Phytoecia* (*Opsilia* Mulsant, 1862) is wrongly accepted as genus name *Opsilia* Mulsant, 1862 by Sama (2023).

p. 330. *Phytoecia* (*Obereina*) *melanocephala* (Fabricius, 1787) was published by G.Sama as *Blepisanis melanocephala*. According to Danilevsky (2018), *Phytoecia* (*Blepisanis* Pascoe, 1867) with the type species from South Africa *Saperda bohemani* Pascoe, 1858 is a purely African taxon.

p. 367. *Psapharochrus jaspideus* (Germar, 1824) was accepted by G.Sama, though it was declared by him as a wrong generic attribution.

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M.A. Lazarev

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В связи с Федеральным законом от 29 декабря 1994 г. № 77-ФЗ «Об обязательном экземпляре документов», экземпляры сдаются в «Российскую книжную палату / филиал ИТАР-ТАСС». Один экземпляр остается в «РКП / филиал ИТАР-ТАСС», который является единственным источником Государственной регистрации отечественных произведений печати и отражения их в государственных библиографических указателях.

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Осуществляется дополнительная адресная рассылка по территории РФ и за рубежом.

ABOUT THE JOURNAL

Humanity space (Гуманитарное пространство. Международный альманах = Humanity space. International almanac) has been published since 2012. Articles that are the result of scientific research are published. Texts could be original researches, containing new, previously unpublished results, surveys, analytical and conceptual manuscripts on specific issues of the humanities and natural sciences.

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Additional targeted mailing is carried out on the territory of the Russian Federation and abroad.

Содержание // Contents

Лазарев М.А. Новая монография Д. Сама (2023) о жуках-усачах (Coleoptera, Cerambycidae) Северной Африки: замечания и обсуждение	
Lazarev M.A. A new monograph by G. Sama (2023) on Longicorn beetles (Coleoptera, Cerambycidae) of North Africa: remarks and discussion.....	414
О ЖУРНАЛЕ	421
ABOUT THE JOURNAL	422